

The preparation of Thorium Phosphate Gels.

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Thorium phosphate gels were first prepared by Satya Prakash (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 587) by mixing solutions of suitable concentrations of thorium nitrate and potassium phosphate. He first obtained a precipitate which disappeared on shaking and resulted in the formation of a more or less opaque solution. On keeping the solution for sometime, it set to a firm transparent gel imbibing within itself all the liquid present in the solution.

It has been found that these gels can be easily prepared if a solution of phosphoric acid is used instead of that of potassium phosphate. In this case only a slight precipitate is obtained and it disappears quickly on shaking. The resulting solution instead of being opaque is quite clear and sets to a firm transparent gel which does not synerise.

It will be seen that in the above methods of preparation, the precipitate of thorium phosphate is peptised to a sol by the hydrogen and thorium ions present in the gel-forming mixture and this process is greatly accelerated by shaking. But it is known that thorium phosphate is insoluble in dilute mineral acids and dissolves readily in the concentrated ones. Therefore, it should be possible to prepare thorium phosphate sol by diluting a solution of thorium phosphate in concentrated acids. In this case the colloidal micelles will be formed by the aggregation or condensation of the molecules of thorium phosphate.

For this purpose, a saturated solution of pure thorium phosphate (7.2 g.) was made in hydrochloric acid (400 c.c. of 4 N-HCl) and 1 c.c. of this solution was diluted to different extent by the addition of distilled water. Nothing separated out when 1 c.c. of the solution was added to 1 c.c. of water. But when it was added to 2 c.c. of water slightly opalescent, hydrated flakes separated out. This

observation definitely disproves the statement (Mellor, "Inorganic Chemistry", vol. VII, p. 252) that a solution of thorium phosphate in a strong mineral acid does not throw out the precipitate on dilution.

On further increasing the dilution by 1 c.c. upto 30 c.c., it was found that thorium phosphate gels were formed. Some of these gels were slightly opalescent, while those formed with higher dilution were quite transparent and rigid. When 1 c.c. of the solution was diluted with more than 30 c.c. of water, only a transparent and homogeneous viscous mass was obtained, *i.e.*, no visible separation of the precipitate took place.

From a long series of experiments on precipitations, Von Weimarn has derived the expression

$$N = V \frac{P}{L}$$

where N represents the "form coefficient" of the precipitate, V is a function of the viscosity of the reaction system, P , the excess of concentration of the substance to be precipitated and L its solubility. According to the above equation if N is large, a gel is formed which cannot be resolved by the microscope while if it is small, a precipitate, which may be amorphous or gelatinous, is obtained.

The value of N increases as V and P increase and L decreases. Since the solubility of thorium phosphate in dilute acids is less than that in concentrated ones, the value of L decreases and of P increases when a solution of thorium phosphate in concentrated acids is diluted. Further the value of V is large because thorium phosphate has a great tendency for hydration. Thus in the case of thorium phosphate, conditions are favourable for the formation of a gel by the dilution method. These observations, therefore, support Weimarn's theory in a qualitative manner. These experiments also show that the gelling substance is a solid and hence in the case of these gels the liquid-liquid theory of gel structure cannot be upheld.

An interesting observation on the above mode of preparing the gels was made when thorium phosphate gels prepared from thorium nitrate and phosphoric acid were dehydrated. Two sets of gels (*i*) containing the same amount of phosphoric acid and different amounts of thorium nitrate and, (*ii*) containing the same amount of thorium nitrate and different amounts of phosphoric acid, were desiccated over phosphorous pentoxide and they were observed to shrink and lose

their form. When the volume of these gels was reduced to about one sixth of the original, the whole mass was converted to a clear transparent solution. The liquid phase did not appear in all gels simultaneously; it appeared earliest in gels containing the least amount of phosphoric acid and the largest amount of thorium nitrate.

The appearance of the liquid phase is due to the fact that as the water content of the gels decreases on dehydration, the H-ion concentration in the gel is increased and thorium phosphate first passes into a colloidal state and then goes into solution. On increasing the amount of phosphoric acid, a greater amount of thorium phosphate is formed and this requires a larger H-ion concentration for solution and hence the appearance of the liquid phase is delayed. Large amounts of thorium nitrate cause the appearance of this phase earlier as thorium ions assist the peptising action of H-ions. These observations conclusively show that thorium phosphate gels can only be obtained when the H-ion concentration of the gel-forming mixtures is below a definite value.

If water is slowly added to the solution, obtained by dehydrating a gel or if the solution is put in an atmosphere of water vapour at reduced pressure, it absorbs water, increases in volume and sets down to a firm gel once again. Thus the reversible sol-gel transformation which is peculiar to organic jellies and is caused by changes in temperature, can be observed in thorium phosphate gel, as well, by dehydrating and hydrating the gel prepared from thorium nitrate and phosphoric acid.